

PRODUCT COSTING: METHODOLOGY AND PRACTICAL APPROACHES

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Abstract. *The costing process plays an important role in the economy and serves to improve the efficiency of the enterprise, cost management and financial results. This article analyzes in detail the essence, importance and role of costing in the economy. It also examines the classification of costs, the costing unit and its stages, cost accounting and costing objects, and the processes of organizing and implementing costing from a scientific and practical perspective.*

Keywords: *calculation, cost, production, technological, efficiency, depreciation, expense.*

Introduction. The emergence of accounting dates back to the creation of humanity, but just as the concept of accounting emerged through the development of humanity, calculation also emerged through the early economic relations of man, this concept gained its scientific basis in the second half of the 19th century.

The first approaches were observed in ancient civilizations, for example, in Mesopotamia, Egypt and Rome. During these periods, calculations were mainly aimed at collecting taxes, determining the cost of construction projects and managing resources.

In the activities of enterprises, the process of calculating the cost of products (works, services) plays an important role in ensuring the rational use of financial resources and increasing efficiency. Calculation is a necessary tool for assessing the economic indicators of the enterprise and implementing financial planning. Cost calculation is one of the main tasks of accounting. The costs associated with the preparation of materials, production of products, performance of work and provision of services are grouped in a current manner in separate accounting accounts. Determining the cost of a unit of finished products, performed work and services is called costing in accounting.

Calculation in a broad sense means the formation of information about the cost of products (works, services) in order to bring costs into a single system and increase production efficiency. In a narrow sense, it is a method of summarizing costs in a single monetary unit and grouping them by type of product (work, service).

All costs are expressed in a single monetary unit, grouped by relevant areas and are calculated as the cost of a unit of product (work, service). Although this process seems simple, it is actually a complex and labor-intensive process. These problems have given rise to a special theory of costing and various practical aspects of costing. Costing is of great importance in production planning, management and efficiency assessment.

The complexity of the costing process is associated with the organizational and technological conditions of production. This complexity arises when choosing the basis for grouping costs. Factors such as the costing object, cost element and cost items are important criteria for grouping costs.

The main part. Costing is one of the important processes within the enterprise. Therefore, it is not formed by a single process. Costing is carried out in a specific form in each of the economic processes. In the supply process, the actual cost of production resources is calculated, in the production process, the technological cost of products and the production cost of products, and in the sales process, the full cost of the product. Costing in economic processes is divided into 3 types:

- Technologic
- Production
- Absolute

Costing requires categorizing costs according to the complexity of the processes carried out in the enterprise, which certainly helps to simplify and calculate it [1].

Technological costing includes the costs of raw materials, materials, fuel, and energy used in the production process. Technological costing is widely used in industrial enterprises, especially in the chemical, automotive, and metallurgical industries, and it can be used to minimize the costs required to produce a product.

In addition to technological costing, production costing includes other costs related to the preparation of a product (for example, losses from unusable products, general production costs). This cost is important in the construction and agricultural sectors of the industry, since the production process in these areas can be long and complex. Full costing includes all costs from the production of a product to its delivery to consumers. Full costing also includes logistics, marketing, and service costs. This type is widespread in the service and trade sectors, including retail and transportation services. [5] [6]

To determine the cost price, it is necessary to take into account the costs of each of the economic processes, namely, supply, production and sale. Therefore, it is necessary to review the Regulation "On the composition of costs of production and sale of products (work, services) and the formation of financial results", which is the methodological basis for calculating the cost of products manufactured, works performed and services provided in the Republic of Uzbekistan, which was put into practice from January 1, 1995 and revised by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 54 of February 5, 1999.

List of costs and period costs included in the cost of products (works, services) in accordance with this Regulation:

Costs included in the cost of production of a product:

- a) direct and indirect material costs;
- b) direct and indirect labor costs;
- c) other direct and indirect costs, including overhead costs of a production nature;

Expenses that are not included in the cost of production, but are included in the profit from the main activity and are included in **the expenses of the period:**

- a) selling expenses;
- b) management expenses (administrative expenses);
- c) other operating expenses and losses;

The following are the expenses of a business entity on its financial activities that are taken into account when calculating the profit or loss from its general economic activities:

- a) interest expenses;
- b) negative exchange rate differences on foreign currency transactions;
- c) revaluation of funds invested in securities;
- g) other expenses on financial activities; [6]

In order to facilitate cost analysis and financial planning, increase efficiency, and comply with legal requirements, it is important to group the costs included in the cost structure based on their economic nature. Therefore, the cost structure that forms the cost structure is as follows:

- material costs in production;
- labor costs in production;
- social contributions to employees in production;
- depreciation of fixed assets and intangible assets in production;
- other costs of a production nature; [4]

Material costs in production include the costs of raw materials, supplies, fuel, and energy used in the production process. Material costs constitute the bulk of the cost of production and are a key indicator of production efficiency.

Labor costs in production refer to the wages paid to workers and specialists. Labor costs are especially important in determining costs in labor-intensive industries, such as agriculture and the service sector.

Social security costs of employee compensation are related to wages and include contributions to social insurance funds and other social payments. They play an important role in improving working conditions and ensuring the well-being of employees.

Depreciation of fixed assets and intangible assets refers to the inclusion of depreciation (**amortization**) of equipment, buildings, and structures used in production. Amortization of intangible assets (for example, patents and licenses) also falls into this group.

Other production costs include additional elements such as various losses, additional services, transportation and marketing costs. These costs make the cost more complex and serve to increase the competitiveness of the product in the market.

Calculations are divided into the following main types according to their purpose:

- plan calculation;
- normative calculation;
- expected calculation;
- actual calculation;

Plan calculation is used to determine the estimated cost of a product or service. Plan costing plays a key role in managing the production process, creating financial plans, and determining pricing policies. It is usually used to determine the cost before starting the production of a new product and to assess the economic efficiency of projects. Therefore, the plan costing of the product should be less than the normative costing.

Normative calculation determines the cost of a product or service based on the calculation of normative costs. In this costing process, calculations are made based on standards and norms.

The expected calculation is compiled by agricultural enterprises as of October 1, based on data on actual expenses incurred and products received in the first three quarters (nine months), as well as an estimated calculation of expected expenses and products received in the fourth quarter. It is of great importance in predicting the production results of each sector and the entire farm for the current year.

Actual calculation determines the actual cost of manufactured products and is usually used to determine the variance between the planned and standard costing. [1]

The concept of cost accounting and product cost calculation means the use of analytical accounting methods and procedures for determining the cost value of products, work performed and services provided by objects of cost calculation. Of course, each enterprise must reflect the

method used in cost accounting and product cost calculation in the enterprise's accounting policy. Which method an enterprise uses depends on the industry in which the enterprise operates.

The simple (process) method is usually used in companies and enterprises that produce large volumes and one type of products. In this process, all costs are determined at the production stages and divided by the volume of the product, the cost of one unit of the product is determined.

The piecewise (semi-finished) method is used in the processing of industrial products. This method is often widespread in metallurgy, textiles, and similar industries. In this method, costs are calculated separately at different stages. However, the final cost is not determined.

The piecewise (semi-finished) method brings the semi-finished products that appear at the stages of the production process to the state of the final product, that is, the costs at each stage are calculated separately and the cost of the final product is calculated. This method is widely used in the automotive industry.

The custom method is widely used in enterprises that produce unique or special items. Examples of these include shipbuilding, aircraft construction, and Rolls Royce, a car manufacturer.

The normative method is one of the widely used methods of calculating the cost of a product. In this method, the cost of a product or service is calculated based on predetermined standard indicators. Standards include the average consumption of labor, materials, energy and other production resources. In this method, the actual cost calculation is determined by adding up the standard cost, the standard cost correction as a result of changes in the standard, and the deviations from the standard in terms of output. Although this method is labor-intensive, it ensures reliable and accurate cost accounting.

The standard-cost method is based on established standard cost indicators for calculating costs in production. In this method, calculations are made based on predetermined standard (standard) indicators instead of actual costs. The standard-cost method is effectively used in planning, control and management.

The direct-cost system, created by American economist Jonathan Harrison in 1936, helps to calculate the cost of a product based on variable costs and determine marginal revenue. Only direct costs are included in the cost of a product. Indirect costs are accounted for separately. Using the direct-cost system, the break-even point, in other words, profitability, is determined and the break-even price for selling a product is determined.

Currently, the direct-cost system is widely used in all economically developed countries. In Germany and Austria, it is called "private cost accounting", in Great Britain, "marginal cost accounting", in France, "marginal accounting" or "marginal accounting". [8, 1]

Summary. In conclusion, this article has revealed several new and relevant points in the economic analysis of the costing process. The article not only explains the essence of costing, but also analyzes in detail its various stages and applications in practice. Additional concepts related to the classification of costs and the costing unit are introduced, which will help to form innovative approaches for enterprises. Advanced methods for accurate cost calculation and cost optimization are presented. Also, this article recommends ways to strengthen economic stability by showing the impact of the costing process on the overall efficiency of the enterprise. This article serves as an important scientific and practical guide, especially for those who want to gain an understanding of innovative solutions aimed at optimizing costs and increasing enterprise efficiency.

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